

E-INCLUSION AND DIGITAL DIVIDE IN HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA : ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

E-inclusion delineates the participation of everyone in the society in digital information cum knowledge sources. It promotes equitable access to digital information or digital knowledge resources. The digital divide among the developed and developing countries, rich and poor, educated and uneducated remains a hindrance in the society for dissemination of information or learning resources to great extent. National Education Policy 2020 emphasized on extensive use of technology in education and addressed reducing the digital divide for maximum dissemination of digital education. With the advancement of information technology, there is the rapid creation of new knowledge. The Digital Explosion of knowledge domains is increasing significantly faster in the 21st-century global world where we are connected by technology. However, the digital divide poses great threats to sustainable development goals; specifically goal number four quality education and goal number ten reduced inequalities and social inclusion. Nevertheless, somehow many countries especially developing countries like India, fail to achieve sustainable development goals to many extents. The present paper attempts to explore the issues and concerns of the digital divide in the higher education ecosystem in the Indian context. It also reflects on the extent of e-inclusion and the digital divide especially in the teaching-learning system and how the majority of the people in our society will come under the purview of the e-inclusion ecosystem so far as higher education is concerned. This paper also provides an overview of different digital divides, issues, and Government initiatives taken to bridge the gap and digitally empower the learner, especially in higher education institutes.

Keywords : Digital divide, E-Inclusion, Sustainable Development Goals, Digital Information

**“Where is the Wisdom, we have lost in Knowledge?
Where is the knowledge we have lost in Information?” – T.S. Eliot**

Introduction

We are in the era of the digital revolution and a knowledge-driven information society. The boon of information and communication technology (ICT) connects the global world in a single click. Moreover, internet technology with smart phones leads to easy access to global information, documents, data, or any education audio-video content, Podcast, and Vodcast within a short interval of time. However, the knowledge pool doubles every 12 Months, soon to be every 12 hours (Schilling, 2013). United Nations Development Programme's Sustainable development Goals number four is quality education while goal number ten speaks about reduced inequality (United Nations General Assembly, 2015). To address and take care of these sustainable goals there is a need to have greater e-inclusion with minimum digital divide across the nations. In general, the digital divide refers to the disparity between those who have access to Information and communication technology (ICT) with high-speed Internet at home and those who do not. As Globalization and faster modern civilization continue to progress, its ability to generate, store, disseminate, and access information expands exponentially. The expansion of information from all media continues to increase at a phenomenal rate.

Our education system is in the realm of Industrial Revolution 4.0 where intelligent machines automate manufacturing, production playing a pivotal role. Therefore, everyone needs digital and computing skills to handle and deal with intelligent machines and robotics systems. The rapid development of the information society is mediated by educational technology. Distance Education facilitated by the digital platforms, in distance mode enrolment constitutes 11.1 percent of the total enrolment in higher education (Ministry of Education, 2020). Growth in digitalization in the Education sector in India depends on the low access, low-cost personal computers, internet facilities with proper infrastructures. Multi international companies (MNCs) and IT industries from

foreign countries are set up in India for international markets and commercial purposes. It was estimated that more than 60-80 percent of the content on the Internet is in English (Keniston & Kumar, 2003). So, people who are more competent in English are more digitally empowered.

The teaching-learning system and the entire academic ecosystem have taken a paradigm shift from offline mode to online or in blended mode amidst the current pandemic. It is very pertinent to mention that we are moving towards digital and online learning modes apart from the face-to-face traditional system. However, the scope and opportunities for digital learning or online learning are not equally reached to students, learners, and common people across the nation. All the people of society need to have access to digital platforms and digital accessories. The government of India has taken many initiatives for promoting digital access or E-inclusion. Digital divide creates a gap among the common people, students, and the life long learner. To develop a knowledge society, we need to build more access to knowledge sources through internet access. The digital platform will enable us to peruse different online courses, access digital libraries, education websites, and web pages, and connect to the global world through various social media platforms.

Method and Sources of the data:

The method applied in the present study is a secondary analysis of existing data and different stake holders' opinion and a systematic way of literature review with in-depth analysis of the data sets.

E-inclusion for Higher Education in Indian

The e-inclusion delineates the digitally enriched knowledge society where each society member has the opportunity and access to available digital information through technology. E-Inclusion can be defined as how information and communication technologies contribute to equalizing and promoting participation in society at all levels. In other words, it is the situation where everyone in society can participate in the information society. Covid-19 Pandemic brings the issue of e-inclusion to a wide spectrum since the whole teaching-learning system, banking, digital payments, and shopping have shifted in online mode. Moreover, the higher education institutes in India are devoid of adequate ICT infrastructure and

minimum facilities for the digital access of global information. The E-inclusion depends on the following three factors

- Affordable access to technologies
- Accessibility and usability of ICT tools and services
- Ability and skills of all individuals to use these tools.

Theories and Models of E-Inclusion

The '**5 Cs' of the E-inclusion Model** referred to as the ladder model, this framework emphasizes the complexity of e-inclusion by identifying five criteria that influence e-inclusion:

- **Connectivity:** It includes access to Internet connectivity and digital infrastructures.
- **Capability:** The core digital skills and competency to deal with digital machines.
- **Content:** The knowledge and curricular practices in the academic ecosystems
- **Confidence:** It focuses on the self-efficacy of the Individuals.
- **Continuity:** The nurturing and practices of new technologies at par with global capacity and trends.

A cumulative and recursive model of successive kinds of access to digital technologies

Van Dijk (1999, 2002) has very explicitly pointed out the multifaceted aspects of the digital divide. He gave the fourfold barrier in access to digital technologies and categorically mention in his cumulative and recursive model having four barriers and issues these are as follows

- a) **Motivational Access:** Very limited use of ICT, lack of Interest in rational use, and negative attitudes towards technology.
- b) **Material Access:** lack of ICT infrastructure
- c) **Skills Access:** lack of digital competency and skills, user-friendliness of ICT, lack of education and social support.
- d) **Usage Access :** Devoid of opportunities and social inequalities

Figure 1:
Cumulative and recursive model of successive kinds of access to digital technologies, Source- Van Dijk , (1999)

Hewlett-Packard Company (Hp) stated the access to social and economic opportunities of the Digital Age and started campaign World e-Inclusion strategies to reduce the digital divide. E-inclusion is a social movement whose purpose is to close the digital divide, a concept that describes how the world can be divided into people who have access to and can use modern information technology and those who do not. Its goal is to close the gap between industrialized and developing countries while also promoting democracy and mutual understanding. It gives disadvantaged people, such as the impoverished, disabled, and unemployed, more influence.

Understanding the Digital Divides

According to the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, the digital divide is the disparity in access to and usage of information and communication technologies (ICTs) and the internet across individuals, households, enterprises, and geographic locations at various socioeconomic levels (OECD 2001). Race, gender, geography, economic level, and physical ability in skills, knowledge, and capacity to use information and other technologies all contribute to the digital divide. In Higher educational institutes diverse students pursue their academic degrees and come from diverse socio-economic and demographic areas.

Digital Divide and its types in Higher Education Institutes

Access divide : Infrastructure related to ICT and technology for accessing digital information is crucial, but unfortunately, there is a severe lack of minimum infrastructure. Availability of internet facilities and networks at the campus of education is another issue that creates the digital divide. According to the National Statistical Organization, household social consumption on Education in India 2017-2018 survey report, merely 4% of the rural households and 23% of the urban households possessed a computer that means one in 10 households has access to computers across the country (Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2018).

Geographical : Varied geographic and demographic location in India causes unequal distribution of resources and at the same time, there is variation in the availability of services such as internet network facilities. Often remotest areas and many villages are devoid of ICT facilities and internet connectivity.

Gender divide : The gender digital divide is one of the crucial inequalities which is much reflected in the realm of the digital revolution. Many empirical studies show that there is a lesser number of women participation in technology access than men especially in developing countries (Antonio & Tuffley, 2014).

Social divide : Social stratification based on various factors like economic conditions, levels of jobs, and hierarchy in society often reflect on the use of technology at par with global knowledge society.

Digital skills divide : A large no of people is not capable to deal with the technology for accessing the information. Even if they are aware of the way of accessing the information and huge knowledge source but not using it, it also leads to skills divide.

Challenges and Barriers to digital divide and E-inclusion

- **Low Internet penetration:** Due to several factors like rural, urban areas, remotest areas, hilly areas, cross border areas and varied geographical regions lead to low internet

penetration. Cities have 42% Internet-enabled homes while in rural India 15% are connected to the internet (Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, 2018).

- **Electricity and Power supply**-In many parts of the country still electricity supply remains an issue, in some places, electricity availability time maybe 2 to 4 hours a day, and somewhere there is no supply.
- **Economic inequality** : Economic disparity and financial crunches lead to not being able to afford minimum digital infrastructures leads to not accessing the digital platforms and knowledge pools.
- **Social mobility** : In developing countries like India, social hierarchy and position often determine its education levels and availing of modern technological or digital infrastructure.
- **Language barriers** : India is a diverse country with having multicultural and multilingual population. Maximum information contents for Higher Education are in English. Those who are competent in English are more benefited and remaining digital empowered than others who are not proficient in the English language.
- **Content barriers** : Maximum content in higher education is in English, which hinders learning for learners who are not proficient in English. Also, the majority of Website contents and web pages are not written in vernacular languages that create the issue in understanding its intent.
- **Digital competency and technophobia**: Proficiency to deal with digital technology, systems of ICT create a severe issue, many teachers may be good at teaching in the face-to-face mode but due to lack of digital competency they are not able to cope with the new system of teaching-learning.
- **Physical Disabilities** : Many Physically challenged learners in higher education face difficulties in accessing the digital platforms, especially those deprived of adequate infrastructures, personal devices for accessing the internet, and other digital systems.

Parameters of Digital divide

Digital divides create unequal access to huge knowledge sources due to various factors and these factors can be categorical can be put under the following parameters -

Figure 2: Parameters of Digital divided bridging the digital divide for E-inclusion

Digital India initiatives

Digital India is a flagship program under which the Government of India took many initiatives for the digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. Under E-governance includes education, health, banking, agriculture, loan, taxes, and many things are functioning. Some of the initiatives are

- **NME ICT** : National mission on Education through Information and communication technology is one of the prominent centrally sponsored schemes for Higher education. In 2011, the Government of India started this effort. Through this mission, many students in Higher education across the nation get low-cost and affordable device access cum computing devices. Also, it provides high-quality e-content free of cost.

- **Bharat Net Projects (2011)** launched to connect 0.25 million panchayats through an optical fibre that was connecting rural villages.
- **National Digital Literacy Mission (2014) and Digital Saksharta Abhiyan:** The government of India took the initiatives for the digital library where a large collection of e-books, thesis, journals, archive newspaper, magazine, reports, policy documents, and e-contents for different disciplines.
- **Pradhan Mantri Gramin Digital Saksharta Abhiyan (2017)** for digital literacy in rural India.

Blended learning : UGC recently on 20th May 2020 proposed the blended mode of learning. Where 40 percent of the course will be online and 60 percent will be in offline mode (University Grants Commission 2021). This type of initiative will positively bring change in the academic ecosystem and will reduce the digital gap.

ABC (Academic Bank of Credit) : This is an innovative way to learn from different universities in a collaborative approach that can be facilitated by technology.

E-Governance : Government regulating, instructing, and directing the different educational institutes in the country through digital platforms and with technological support. The smooth functioning of the entire educational ecosystem of the country is governed through digital platforms especially or higher education. Government fellowships, scholarships, and different educational loans are transacted through online transactions. However, due to technological limitations and infrastructure issues still in many parts of the country, it leads to digital divides.

MOOCs or SWAYAM Courses : A large number of Massive open online courses (MOOCs) were started by the Government of India especially for college and University students to cater and disseminate the maximum content knowledge for different disciplines.

SWAYAM Prabha : The government of India started to provide 32 High-Quality Education channels through DTH (Direct to Home). Quality educational content by subject experts for diverse disciplines made available across the length and breadth of the

country on a 24*7 basis using GSAT-15 Satellites for telecasts (Swayam Prabha, n.d.).

Virtual labs : Different sciences and Engineering disciplines needed laboratory facilities for a better understanding of the subjects' contents. Therefore with the efforts and initiatives of the Government of India through different IIT, NIT, and Central University started the virtual laboratory especially for students enrolled in Higher Education.

Private Sectors Initiatives for minimizing digital divide and greater E-inclusion : Many telecom industries and organizations offer low-budget internet data plans and broadband subsidies for wide internet access and digital platforms.

Microsoft : Software company providing low-cost computing software and computing system to many developing countries at very low cost and also as philanthropic work they are providing training to many young graduates for skilling aligning with the industrial and corporate Jobs.

Hewlett-Packard Company (Hp) : Hp started campaign World e-Inclusion strategies to reduce the digital divide. They provide low-cost computers and accessories to many developing countries like India which is a noble initiative for greater e-inclusion.

Wipro : Indian Software Company providing financial support to educational institutes for digitally empowering the academic institutes. Also, provide training to teachers and students for enhancing digital competency.

Non-Governmental Organizations Multinational companies: They provide and conduct free skilling training to ongoing graduates in different higher education campuses.

Implications of the digital divide : A digitally empowered society will enable each of us to generate and access greater knowledge pools across the globe. However, due to the digital divide followings implications can be observed-

- Advanced literacy level is severely affectedly urban-rural digital divide
- Job security among people who are not digitally compliant or digitally competent.
- Tech-savvy operations at varying levels
- Personality development

- Economic development of the country at various levels
- Income disparity among the society
- Access to knowledge through the Internet
- Negative impacts on basic literacy rate
- Equity concern among physically challenged or Divyang person access to digital infrastructure.

Reflections from National Education Policy 2020 addressing the digital divide

Nowadays technology becomes our compulsion and not the choice. Moreover one of the core principles of National Education Policy 2020 is the extensive use of technology. It 2020 recognizes the importance of leveraging the advantages of technology while acknowledging its potential risks and dangers. Digital education can be maximum be utilized unless and until we eliminate the digital divide through different efforts such as Digital India Campaign. The rationale use of technology for online and digital education adequately addresses the concerns of equity. Since there is still a significant portion of the population with inadequate digital access, conventional mass media such as television, radio, and community radio will be heavily employed for telecasts and broadcasts. Such instructional programs will be provided 24 hours a day, seven days a week in a variety of languages to meet the diverse demands of the student population. A strong emphasis on content in all Indian languages will be highlighted and necessary; digital content will need to reach instructors and students as much as possible in their medium of instruction.

Concluding Remarks

With globalization and digital technology evolution, there is rapid diffusion of the Internet and new educational technologies to empower the knowledge-driven information society. India is a highly fragmented, diverse socio-economic condition, a stratified society with socio-political influence in different areas of the academic ecosystem. To bridge the digital gap and greater e-inclusion in the higher education sector, there is an urgency in strong political support, government initiatives, and the need to bring necessary policy for access and equity in digital infrastructures and facilities. Technology is not a choice but a compulsion in the academic ecosystem for effective and quality

education. National Education Policy 2020 realizes its importance and gets reflected in one of its core principle that is extensive use of technology in Education. For people with disabilities, digital technologies break down traditional barriers to communication, interaction, and information access. The convergence of increased public and private service provision via Information and Communication Technology (ICT) with the expanding number of mainstream, daily ICTs that can be utilized as accessible devices is shifting the paradigm of technology-enabled development for people with disabilities(Raja, 2016).

National Educational Policy 2020 envisions an equitable and vibrant knowledge society and makes India a global knowledge superpower. To achieve its intent, there is a crucial need for a digitally empowered society and greater e-inclusion in the academic ecosystem, especially in higher education. Positive attitude towards technology and have to accept it for our greater efficiency to access global knowledge pools for assimilating in our cognition. Nevertheless, even if we have access to technology but lack in its rationale and judicious use, it will also lead to a digital divide. Digital competency is the need of the 21st century in all spheres of educational institutes. In India like a developing country we are devoid of necessary infrastructure but need to develop the sharing attitudes of our devices or systems and knowledge pools for greater e-inclusion. We need to find and look for alternatives and all possible means to access technology like digital libraries, Community centers, community libraries, Radio, TV, podcasts, Vodcast, Wi-Fi Zone, MOOCs, Open Educational Resources, and many more. Since the 21st-century global world is looking for collaborations and cooperation, there is a need for greater educational institutional collaboration with various computing and digital laboratories across the globe to reduce the digital divide.

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